

OF CLINICAL DIVERSITY OF TTM**Utayev Akbar Juraqulovich**

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Abstract: The task set before us to write this article was analyze the clinical (psychopathological and dermatological) diversity of TTM. Based on psychopathological characteristics, develop a clinical differentiation of the disorder highlighting the types of TTM. To establish patterns of skin status in various psychopathological types of TTM. To achieve our goals and objectives, we analyzed the study included patients who met the criteria for trichotillomania ICD-10 and DSM-5 (20 cases; 3 men, 17 women, including 7 children under the age of 18 years; average age – 26.6±13.2 years). Patients were examined using an interdisciplinary approach by a psychiatrist and a dermatologist (trichologist). Comprehensive clinical assessment of patients included assessment of dermatological and mental status. As a result, we came to the conclusion that no patterns of skin status have been established in dissociative TTM, which may be due to the small number of observations (2 cases). Discussion The study results demonstrate the clinical heterogeneity of TTM.

Key words: Trichotillomania, treatment, analysis, psychopathological and dermatological, TTM, trichologist, Discussion, auto-extraction, psychopathological.

КЛИНИЧЕСКОЕ РАЗНООБРАЗИЕ ТРИХОТИЛЛОМАНИИ**Утаев Акбар Журакулович**

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Аннотация: Задачей, поставленной перед нами для написания данной статьи, было исследование клинического (психопатологического и дерматологического) разнообразия трихотилломании (ТТМ). На основе психопатологических характеристик разработать клиническую дифференциацию расстройства, выделяя типы ТТМ. Установить закономерности состояния кожи при различных психопатологических типах ТТМ. Для достижения наших целей было проведено исследование, включающее пациентов, соответствующих критериям трихотилломании по МКБ-10 и DSM-5 (20 случаев: 3 мужчины, 17 женщин, из которых 7 детей младше 18 лет; средний возраст — 26,6±13,2 года). Пациенты были обследованы с использованием междисциплинарного подхода психиатра и дерматолога (трихолога). В рамках комплексной клинической оценки пациентов проводилась оценка дерматологического и психического состояния. В результате исследования было установлено, что закономерности состояния кожи не были выявлены при диссоциативной ТТМ, что может быть связано с малым числом наблюдений (2 случая). Обсуждение: Результаты исследования демонстрируют клиническую гетерогенность трихотилломании.

Ключевые слова: трихотилломания, лечение, анализ, психопатологическое и дерматологическое, ТТМ, трихолог, обсуждение, автоизвлечение, психопатологический.

INTRODUCTION

Trichotillomania (TTM) is a psychodermatological disorder with auto-aggressive behavior in relation to hair (auto-extraction). The relevance of studying TTM is due to its

significant prevalence, underdiagnosis, pronounced impact on quality of life, psychological consequences, as well as the uncertainty of the psychopathological structure.

Aim. To analyze the clinical (psychopathological and dermatological) diversity of TTM. Based on psychopathological characteristics, develop a clinical differentiation of the disorder highlighting the types of TTM. To establish patterns of skin status in various psychopathological types of TTM.

Materials and methods. The study included patients who met the ICD-10 and DSM-5 criteria for trichotillomania (20 cases; 3 men, 17 women, including 7 children under the age of 18 years; average age – $26.6 \pm 13,2$ years). Patients were examined using an interdisciplinary approach by a psychiatrist and a dermatologist (trichologist). Comprehensive clinical assessment of patients included assessment of dermatological and mental status.

Results. In the analyzed group, 90% of patients (18 cases) suffered autodestruction of hair on the scalp, of which 10% (2 cases) - in combination with trauma to the eyebrows and eyelashes; 2 patients had isolated damage to the eyebrows and eyelashes. The average age of onset of the disease is 20 years. The average duration of the disease is 6.6 years (± 5.4 years). Three psychodermatological variants of TTM have been identified: the most common is compulsive (12 cases – 60%), less often – impulsive (6 cases – 30%), the rarest is dissociative (2 cases – 10%). In compulsive TTM, the clinical picture is dominated by tactile illusions. They are associated with the perception by touch of individual hairs as different from the rest - others (“uneven”, “crimped”, “hard”), which are subjectively perceived as “wrong” and undergo auto-depilation. It is common to experience an increase in anxiety when trying to resist obsession. After hair removal, a feeling of relief is observed with a reduction in anxious affect. In impulsive TTM, hair extraction is implemented within the framework of impulse control disorders. The bodily sensations are sensations in the form of itching “penetrating” the skin with a projection to the base of the hair, compared by patients with “needles” piercing the skin. At the peak of bodily sensations, a feeling of irritation and dysphoria arises, the reduction of which occurs after the act of extraction. The latter is indiscriminate (hair plucking occurs in groups - “tufts”) and is realized according to the type of generalized vital drive, comparable to hunger or thirst. Following the act of self-destruction, a feeling of internal satisfaction, “pleasure” arises. In dissociative TTM, tactile illusions are not typical; patients pull out hair as if unnoticed by themselves (while busy with activities, in a state of detachment, in a drowsy state). In this case, there is an alienation of pathological habitual actions performed “automatically” with amnesia of the auto-aggressive act. When assessing the skin status in patients with TTM, two types of baldness could be distinguished: in the form of diffuse thinning of hair with unclear outlines (in 8 of 18 cases) and localized foci with clearer figured outlines - round and linear (in 10 of 18 cases). The relationship between dermatological clinical manifestations and the type of TTM is traced. Thus, among patients with localized foci with clearer outlines, the compulsive version of TTM was more common (7 out of 10 cases), with vaguely limited areas of diffuse hair thinning - impulsive (5 out of 8 cases). Patients with compulsive TTM more often carried out pulling out locally in the usual places (where extraction is more convenient, less noticeable, painless). With impulsive TTM, chaotic indiscriminate extraction with the formation of diffuse areas of rarefaction is more typical.

Conclusions: no patterns of skin status have been established in dissociative TTM, which may be due to the small number of observations (2 cases). Discussion The study results demonstrate the clinical heterogeneity of TTM. The identified features of the skin status may be a

consequence of the preferred behavioral pattern of autoextraction of hair (a variant of TTM), although this can be clearly judged only from the results of further research.

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